

C-CWatM Userguide

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1

Introduction

Climate-CWatM (C-CWatM) is a river-routing and water-resources model designed to complement climate, Earth system, and land-surface models. These systems typically simulate land-surface processes in detail but do not represent river routing or human water management. C-CWatM fills this gap by providing a dedicated framework for simulating freshwater flows and human water use, either as a standalone model or coupled to larger modelling systems. Key characteristics of C-CWatM include:

- **Purpose:** Simulation of river routing, water availability, sectoral water demand, and water abstraction from surface water and groundwater.
- **Model design:** A simplified version of the Community Water Model (CWatM), focusing exclusively on river routing and water management.
- **Coupling capability:** Can run in **offline mode**, driven by prescribed land-surface inputs, or in **online mode**, coupled to climate or Earth system models via a coupling interface.
- **Input data:** Uses land-surface variables such as runoff, soil moisture, open-water evaporation, and groundwater recharge, rather than atmospheric forcing.
- **Technical structure:**
 - Grid-based model at daily resolution
 - Modular architecture separating hydrology, water demand, data handling, and coupling
- **Implementation:** Primarily written in Python with performance-critical components in C++, using NetCDF as the main data format and distributed as open-source software.

This user guide provides an overview of the model structure, installation, configuration options, required input data, and available output, enabling users to set up and run C-CWatM efficiently in both standalone and coupled applications.

2

Installation and setup

2.1 Installation and required packages

To set up C-CWatM, Python is required, preferably version 3.7 or newer. The computationally intensive river-routing routines are more effectively integrated using C++. These routines are provided in pre-compiled format, so no additional setup is necessary.

C-CWatM requires a small set of Python packages:

```
numpy
scipy
gdal
netCDF4
pyOASIS
```

In case any of these packages are missing, installation via pip or conda is possible. pyOASIS is required for coupling. However, C-CWatM can run in offline mode without pyOASIS installed.

To use CWatM, download from GitHub (<https://github.com/UWaRes/c-cwatm>) or a git clone is required:

```
git clone https://github.com/UWaRes/c-cwatm.git
```

2.2 Required input maps

C-CWatM standard input data are the same as for CWatM and available at resolutions of 0.5° (<https://github.com/iiasa/CWatM-Earth-30min>) and 0.5' (https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1HqcBj5fD6DHJp0e-t_6JHFMKFtubghZf). Please note that C-CWatM requires a reduced set of input maps as outlined in Sect. 5.2.

2.3 Model runs

C-CWatM can be run from inside the CWatM folder:

```
python run_cwatm.py
```

Ideally, the following output will be generated:

```
Running under platform: Linux (or else)
C-CWatM - Climate-Community Water Model
```

```
Authors: ...
Version: ...
Date: ...
Status: ...
```

```
Arguments list:
settings.ini      settings file

-q --quiet        output progression given as .
-v --veryquiet   no output progression is given
-l --loud        output progression given as time step, date and
discharge
-c --check       input maps and stack maps are checked, output
for each input map BUT no model run
-h --noheader    .tss file have no header and start immediately
with the time series
-t --printtime   the computation time for hydrological modules
are printed
-w --warranty    copyright and warranty information
```

The arguments list contains flags that can be used to control the output during runtime. Using a settingsfile and flags (optional), C-CWatM can be run as following:

```
python run_cwatm.py settingsfile flags
```

Model configuration and processes

3.1 River routing

Method

River flow is routed along a fixed channel network using the kinematic wave approximation, which provides an efficient and robust method for simulating downstream transport of runoff. Routing parameters are derived from channel characteristics, including channel length, slope, width, and depth. Flow velocity is calculated using Manning's equation, ensuring consistency between channel geometry and hydraulic resistance. Channel roughness is represented by Manning's roughness coefficient, which serves as a **calibration parameter** in the model. Routing is performed by the modules in `hydrological_modules/routing_reservoirs/`. Computationally intensive components are implemented in C++ to improve performance.

Data

Required input maps for routing are:

- Channel Manning's n: `chanmanning.nc`
- Channel length: `chanlength.nc`
- Channel bottom width: `chanwidth.nc`
- Bankfull channel depth: `chanheight.nc`

Configuration parameters

```
[ROUTING]

PathRouting = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMaps)/routing

# Number of substep per day
# should be 10 for 0.5 deg but 24 for 0.1 deg
NoRoutingSteps = 10
#kinematic wave parameter: 0.6 is for broad sheet flow
chanBeta = 0.6

# Channel gradient (fraction, dy/dx)
chanGrad = $(PathRouting)/kinematic/changradient.nc
```

```
# Minimum channel gradient (for kin. wave: slope cannot be 0)
chanGradMin = 0.0001

#Channel Manning's n
chanMan = $(PathRouting)/kinematic/chanmanning.nc
#Channel length [meters]
chanLength = $(PathRouting)/kinematic/chanlength.nc
#Channel bottom width [meters]
chanWidth = $(PathRouting)/kinematic/chanwidth.nc
#Bankfull channel depth [meters]
chanDepth = $(PathRouting)/kinematic/chanheight.nc
```

3.2 Reservoirs and lakes

Method

Reservoirs and lakes are integrated into the river channel network and are classified as global or local water bodies based on their size and contributing catchment area. This classification depends on the spatial resolution of the model. Global reservoirs and lakes are located on the main river channel of a grid cell and are connected to the entire upstream catchment. They directly influence routed river discharge. Local reservoirs and lakes, by contrast, are contained within a single grid cell and interact only with locally generated runoff. They are not connected to the main river network.

Reservoir operation follows a rule-based scheme adapted from the LISFLOOD model [Burek et al., 2013]. Reservoirs are operated within a defined normal storage range to maintain relatively stable outflows, for example to support hydropower production. Outflow depends on reservoir storage and inflow conditions and is constrained by minimum and maximum limits to ensure ecological minimum flows and to limit downstream flooding.

Lakes are simulated using a simplified flood-retention approach based on the modified Puls method [Chow et al., 1998, Burek et al., 2013]. Lake storage changes are calculated from inflows from upstream channels and losses due to outflow and evaporation. Lake outflow is controlled by water level and outlet characteristics, using simplified assumptions on geometry and flow dynamics. In the original CWatM implementation, lake evaporation is estimated from potential evaporation over water surfaces. In C-CWatM, this process is simplified by prescribing open-water evaporation as an external forcing field.

Calculations for large lakes and reservoirs are handled within `hydrological_modules/lakes_reservoirs.py` and for small lakes in `hydrological_modules/lakes_res_small.py`.

Data

The following datasets derived from the HydroLakes database are used in the implementation: For big lakes and reservoirs:

- Lake ID: `lakesResID.nc`
- Type: `lakesResType.nc`
- Average discharge: `lakesResDis.nc`
- Surface area: `lakesResArea.nc`

For small lakes: `smallLakesRes.nc` and `smallLakesResDis.nc`

For reservoirs:

- reservoir volume: lakesResVolRes.nc
- starting year: lakesResYear.nc

Configuration parameters

```
[LAKES_RESERVOIRS]

PathLakesRes = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMaps)/routing/lakesreservoirs

# Use reservoirs and lakes (otherwise use only lakes Lake ID=1 and
  3 => natural conditions)
useResAndLakes = True
# Reservoirs do have a year of implementation
dynamicLakesRes = True
# if Reservoirs does not have a year of implementation, which year
  should be taken as fixed year
fixLakesResYear = 1950

# --- Big lakes and Reservoirs ---

# ID of every lake, reservoir from HydroLakes database
waterBodyID = $(PathLakesRes)/lakesResID.nc
# 1 for lake, 2 for reservoir, 3 for lake and reservoir
waterBodyTyp = $(PathLakesRes)/lakesResType.nc
# Avergae discharge from HydroLakes Database
waterBodyDis = $(PathLakesRes)/lakesResDis.nc
# Lakes surface area from HydroLakes Database
waterBodyArea = $(PathLakesRes)/lakesResArea.nc
# Create a buffer around water bodies as command areas for lakes
  and reservoirs
buffer_waterbodies = 2

# Optional: reservoir command areas
# using_reservoir_command_areas = False
# reservoir_command_areas =
# commandAreasRelaxGwAbstraction =

# limit res. outflows to reservoir with water level >
  limit_to_resOutflows
# limit_to_resOutflows is defined relative to res. Volume [0.-1.]
# limit_to_resOutflows = 1.

# --- Small lakes and reservoirs ---

useSmallLakes = True

smallLakesRes = $(PathLakesRes)/smallLakesRes.nc
smallwaterBodyDis = $(PathLakesRes)/smallLakesResDis.nc
# optional: set a minimum volume for small lakes and reservoirs,
  default = 9.e99
# minStorage = 10.

# --- Reservoirs ---
# reservoir volume from HydroLakes database
waterBodyVolRes = $(PathLakesRes)/lakesResVolRes.nc
# reservoir starting year from HydroLakes database
waterBodyYear = $(PathLakesRes)/lakesResYear.nc
```

```

# Conservative, normal and flood storage limit (fraction of total
# storage, [-])
conservativeStorageLimit = 0.1
#normalStorageLimit = 0.5 # --> put into calibration
floodStorageLimit = 0.9
# adjusting the balance between normal and flood storage
# [0 ..1] 0: NormalstorageLimit      1: (= closer to flood)
# results in keeping the normal qoutflow longer constant
adjust_Normal_Flood = 0.5

# Minimum, Normal and Non-damaging reservoir outflow (fraction of
# average discharge, [-])
MinOutflowQ = 0.2
NormalOutflowQ = 1.0
NonDamagingOutflowQ = 4.0

```

3.3 Groundwater

Method

Following the methodology used in the LISFLOOD model [De Roo et al., 2000, Udias et al., 2016], groundwater storage and baseflow are represented using a linear reservoir approach. This means that the outflow from the groundwater zone (baseflow Q_{base}) is proportional to the groundwater storage:

$$Q_{base} = R_{coeff} \cdot Storage, \quad (3.1)$$

with the recession coefficient R_{coeff} determining the outflow rate. This recession coefficient also serves as a calibration parameter within the model. The groundwater reservoir is filled only by drainage from the lower soil zone (provided as forcing, see Sect. 5.1.3). It is emptied by baseflow and by abstractions due to human water use (Sect. 3.4). Groundwater calculations are handled within `cwatm/hydrological_modules/groundwater.py`.

Data

A global map of the baseflow recession coefficient is provided in the file named:

`recessionCoeff.nc`

It is multiplied by the calibration parameter `recessionCoeff_factor` within the model.

Configuration parameters

```

[GROUNDWATER]

PathGroundwater = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMaps)/groundwater

recessionCoeff = $(PathGroundwater)/recessionCoeff.nc
# baseflow = recessionCoeff * storage groundwater
# both not used at the moment in groundwater modul, but already
# loaded

# If zonal abstraction is not enabled, it assumes full fossil
# groundwater abstraction

```

```

# is allowed and sets sectoral abstractions equal to their
  potential values.
zonal_abstraction = False

# optional: inner grid size of allocation zone
# allocation_area = 1.

```

3.4 Human water use

Human water use in C-CWatM includes demand and consumption by livestock (3.4.1), households (3.4.3), industry (3.4.2) and irrigation (3.4.4). Additionally, an environmental flow cap can be set and sector source abstractions can be prescribed.

```

[OPTIONS]
# if irrigation is included, otherwise paddy and non paddy is
# put into 'grassland'
includeIrrigation = True
# if False, all irrigation is nonpaddy, if True, paddy irrigation
# is calculated based on
# a simple approach (like nonpaddy, but with alpha depletion = 1)
paddy_irrig = True
# if water demand from irrigation, industry, domestic is included
includeWaterDemand = True
# limit abstraction to available groundwater (True) include fossil
  groundwater (False)
limitAbstraction = False
# fossil water that is not consumed is not lost, but treated
  normally
fossil_water_treated_normally = True
# Environmental Flow
# dynamic part of environflow.py is only called if True
calc_environflow = False

[WATERDEMAND]
# Demand in m/day [True] (default) or as mio m3 per year
# or month [False]
demand_unit = False

```

`includeIndusDomesDemand` is automatically `True` if `includeWaterDemand = True`. It can be overwritten with `includeIndusDomesDemand = False` (then, only irrigation and environmental flow are considered).

3.4.1 Livestock

Method

Livestock water consumption is estimated based on the livestock densities in each grid cell. Each of the livestock types considered has distinct drinking water requirements, which vary monthly as a function of air temperature. There are six different livestock types: cattle, buffalo, sheep, goats, pigs and poultry. The approach is taken from [Wada et al. \[2011\]](#).

Livestock water demand is handled within `cwatm/hydrological_modules/water_demand/livestock.py` and stored in the variables `self.var.livestockDemand` (demand read from file) and `self.var.pot_livestockConsumption` (equals demand). It is assumed that there are no return flows and thus the gross demand equals the net demand.

Data

Gridded livestock densities and their drinking water requirements for each of the six livestock types are taken from [FAO \[2007\]](#) and [Steinfeld et al. \[2006\]](#). They have a resolution of 5' and are available for the year 2000. The numbers of each livestock type are available on a country level for the years 1979 to 2010 and provided by [[FAO et al., 2012](#)]. They are downscaled to the model resolution using the gridded densities of 2000. The combined dataset is provided in the file named:

```
historical_liv_year_millionm3_5min_1961_2010.nc
```

Configuration parameters

```
[WATERDEMAND]
uselivestock = True
livestockWaterDemandFile = $(FILE_PATHS:PathWaterdemand)/
                           historical_liv_year_millionm3_5min_1961_2010.nc
livestockTimeMonthly = False
livestockvarname = livestockConsumption
```

Livestock water consumption is only considered if `uselivestock = True`. The data are read from the netCDF-file provided in `livestockWaterDemandFile` under the variable given in `livestockvarname`. The data are either yearly (`livestockTimeMonthly = False`) or could also be provided with monthly values.

3.4.2 Industry

Method

The calculation of the industrial water demand follows the method of [Shen et al. \[2008\]](#) and [Wada et al. \[2011\]](#). Values are obtained by multiplying a water use intensity index with a gridded dataset of industrial water demand for 2000 [based on [Shiklomanov, 1997](#)]. Water use intensity is derived from per capita values for gross domestic product (GDP), electricity production, energy consumption, and household consumption, capturing both economic and technological development.

According to [Wada et al. \[2011\]](#), the water use index (WUI) on a country level (cnt) is the product of an economic development factor (EDev) and a technological development factor (TDev):

$$\text{WUI}_{\text{cnt}} = \text{EDev}_{\text{cnt}} \times \text{TDev}_{\text{cnt}}. \quad (3.2)$$

EDev is the average of the development of per capita values for GDP, electricity production, energy consumption, and household consumption, which are expressed in the form of $\sqrt{X_{\text{past}}/X_{\text{present}}}$. The energy consumption per unit electricity production is used to approximate technological development (TDev).

Return flows are the portion of the water withdrawn for industrial purposes that is returned to the river system after use. Consequently, the net water demand, representing actual consumption, is adjusted by a return rate of 90 % reported by [Shiklomanov \[2000\]](#).

Industrial water demand data is read from a file within `cwatm/hydrological_modules/water_demand/industry.py` and stored in the variables `self.var.industryDemand` (withdrawal, gross demand) and `self.var.pot_industryConsumption` (net consumption).

Data

Gridded industrial water demand data is provided by [Shiklomanov \[1997\]](#) at 5' resolution, which is then multiplied by a water use intensity index. The combined dataset is provided in the file named:

```
historical_ind_year_millionm3_5min_1961_2010.nc
```

Configuration parameters

```
[WATERDEMAND]
industryWaterDemandFile = $(FILE_PATHS:PathWaterdemand)/
                        historical_ind_year_millionm3_5min_1961_2010.nc
industryTimeMonthly = False
industryWithdrawalvarname = indWW
industryConsumptionvarname = indCon
```

Data for industrial water demand are read from the netCDF-file provided in the variable `industryWaterDemandFile` with gross demand under `industryWithdrawalname` and net demand under `industryConsumptionvarname`. The data are either yearly or could also be provided with monthly values (`industryTimeMonthly = True`).

3.4.3 Domestic

Method

Domestic water demand is calculated by multiplying the same water use intensity index as for industrial demand (see Sect. 3.4.2) with the number of persons per grid cell and a county-specific per capita water withdrawal. Seasonal variability is considered by using air temperature as a proxy, with higher demand in warmer months [[Wada et al., 2011](#)]. Return flows for domestic water use To obtain the net domestic water demand, representing actual consumption, the gross demand is adjusted by a return rate of 85 % reported by [Shiklomanov \[2000\]](#).

Industrial water demand data is read from a file within `cwatm/hydrological_modules/water_demand/domestic.py` and stored in the variables `self.var.domesticDemand` (withdrawal, gross demand) and `self.var.pot_domesticConsumption` (net consumption).

Data

Domestic water demand used data of the population in a grid cell of 5' and a country-specific per capita domestic water withdrawal rate taken from [FAO et al. \[2012\]](#) and [Gleick et al. \[2009\]](#). The combined dataset is provided in the file named:

```
historical_dom_year_millionm3_5min_1961_2010.nc
```

Configuration parameters

```
[WATERDEMAND]
domesticWaterDemandFile = $(FILE_PATHS:PathWaterdemand)/
                        historical_dom_year_millionm3_5min_1961_2010.nc
domesticTimeMonthly = False
domesticWithdrawalvarname = domWW
domesticConsumptionvarname = domCon
```

Data for domestic water demand are read from the netCDF-file provided in the variable `domesticWaterDemandFile` with gross demand under `domesticWithdrawalname` and net demand under `domesticConsumptionvarname`. The data are either yearly or could also be provided with monthly values (`domesticTimeMonthly = True`).

3.4.4 Irrigation

Method

Paddy irrigation for rice fields and irrigation for other crops are treated separately when calculating irrigation water withdrawal and consumption.

For **non-paddy crops**, irrigation water demand follows the standard approach used in CWatM [Burek et al., 2020]. The demand is calculated as the difference between a target soil water content and the currently available water in the root zone. The target soil water content is defined as the available water capacity between field capacity (FC) and wilting point (WP), scaled by an alpha-depletion factor (α). This factor can be specified in the settings file or used as a calibration parameter. The available water is computed from the current soil water content in the root zone:

$$WD_{\text{irri}} = \alpha(\text{FC} - \text{WP}) - (\text{SWC} - \text{WP}), \quad (3.3)$$

The root zone soil water content (SWC) is derived from the forcing field `rootzoneSM` and the maximum soil water storage capacity. Spatial datasets for FC, WP, and soil water storage capacity are provided as input maps and can be adapted to match characteristics from the driving land surface or climate model.

Irrigation demand is constrained by the maximum soil infiltration capacity and a minimum irrigation threshold to avoid numerical artifacts. Irrigation is applied only during the crop growing season, which is determined using crop coefficient data. Water withdrawals are adjusted for conveyance losses, return flows, and evaporation during irrigation using an irrigation water-use efficiency factor. This factor can be prescribed as spatial efficiency maps or specified as a constant value.

In the original CWatM implementation, **paddy irrigation** is simulated by maintaining a constant surface water depth of 50 mm. This approach requires information on paddy water levels, which is typically not available from land surface or climate model forcing data. Therefore, C-CWatM adopts a simplified representation of paddy irrigation. Paddy irrigation in C-CWatM follows the same soil-moisture-based approach as non-paddy irrigation, but with a fixed target soil water content equal to field capacity. This corresponds to setting the alpha-depletion factor to $\alpha = 1$, ensuring that paddy fields are maintained at field capacity throughout the growing season.

Calculations are performed within the module `/hydrological_modules/water_demand/irrigation.py`.

Data

Irrigation calculations require various landcover and soil input maps (see below).

Configuration parameters

```
[WATERDEMAND]
historicalIrrigationArea =
  $(FILE_PATHS:PathWaterdemand)/irrigationArea.nc
irrNonPaddy_efficiency = 0.8
irrPaddy_efficiency = 0.8
```

```

irrigation_returnfraction = 0.5

[SOIL]
PathSoil = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMaps)/soil_ccwatm
# soil storage capacity
wsp = $(PathSoil)/wsirr.nc
# field capacity
wfc = $(PathSoil)/wfcirr.nc
# wilting point
wwpp = $(PathSoil)/wwpirr.nc
# Different constants
minCropKC = 0.2

[LANDCOVER]
[__irrPaddy]
PathIrrPaddy = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMaps)/landcover/irrPaddy
irrPaddy_minInterceptCap = 0.001
irrPaddy_cropCoefficientNC =
$(PathIrrPaddy)/cropCoefficientirrPaddy_10days.nc
# maximum flooding depth for paddy
irrPaddy_maxtopwater = 0.05

[__irrNonPaddy]
PathIrrNonPaddy = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMaps)/landcover/irrNonPaddy
irrNonPaddy_minInterceptCap = 0.001
irrNonPaddy_cropCoefficientNC =
$(PathIrrNonPaddy)/cropCoefficientirrNonPaddy_10days.nc

```

4

The settings file

4.1 General settings

These settings define the basic structure and scope of the model run.

[OPTIONS]

This section contains switches that enable or disable specific model components and processes. These options allow users to tailor the simulation to their study objectives and available data.

Data handling:

- **TemperatureInKelvin: Boolean flag indicating temperature unit.** If True, input temperature is assumed to be in Kelvin; otherwise, Celsius.
- **gridSizeUserDefined: Specifies whether the grid size is user-defined.** If True, the model uses a predefined grid size rather than calculating it internally.
- **no_meteo: Enables use of externally provided hydrological variables.** If True, the model reads runoff, soil moisture, groundwater recharge, and open water evaporation from input maps instead of calculating them from meteorological data.

Irrigation and water demand:

- **includeIrrigation: Enables irrigation processes.** If False, irrigated areas are treated as grassland.
- **paddy_irrig: Specifies type of irrigation.** If False, all irrigation is treated as non-paddy. *Note: Paddy irrigation is not yet supported.*
- **includeWaterDemand: Includes water demand from irrigation, industry, and domestic sectors.**
- **limitAbstraction: Restricts groundwater abstraction to available resources.** If True, abstraction is limited to renewable groundwater; if False, fossil groundwater may be used.
- **fossil_water_treated_normally: Controls treatment of unused fossil water.** If True, unused fossil water is retained in the system.
- **calc_envirflow: Enables calculation of environmental flow requirements.**

Routing and flow processes:

- **includeRunoffConcentration:** Includes runoff concentration to cell edges. Typically set to `False` in C-CWatM.
- **includeWaterBodies:** Includes lakes and reservoirs in the routing scheme.
- **includeRouting:** Activates kinematic wave routing. If `False`, no routing is performed.
- **inflow:** Includes inflow from outside the modeled domain.

Reporting and output control:

- **writeNetcdfStack:** Enables writing of NetCDF output stacks.
- **reportMap:** Generates spatial output maps.
- **reportTss:** Generates time series output files.

[FILE_PATHS]

This section defines the directory structure for all input and output data used in a C-CWatM model run. These paths are referenced throughout the settings file to locate maps, meteorological data, masks, and output directories. Paths can be absolute or relative, but must be accessible from the system running the model. Ensure all required files exist in the specified directories before running the model.

- **PathRoot:** Root directory for input data. This is the base path from which other input paths are derived.
- **PathOut:** Directory for model output.
- **PathMaps:** Directory for static map inputs. Typically set to $\$(PathRoot)$ to reuse the root path. ??
- **PathMask:** Directory for area mask maps. Used to define the spatial extent of the model domain.
- **PathMeteo:** Directory for meteorological forcing data.
- **PathWaterdemand:** Directory for water demand data. Includes data required to estimated domestic, industrial, livestock, and irrigation water demand.

[TIME-RELATED_CONSTANTS]

This section defines the temporal scope and structure of the model simulation. All dates are in DD/MM/YYYY format.

- **StepStart:** Start date of the simulation. This marks the beginning of the model run.
- **SpinUp:** Optional spin-up period. If specified, the model will run from **StepStart** to **SpinUp** without generating output, allowing the system to stabilize.
- **StepEnd:** End date of the simulation. This marks the final day of the simulation period.

[INITIAL CONDITIONS]

This section defines how the model handles initial states for a simulation run. These settings are particularly useful for warm starts, where the model begins from a previously saved state rather than initializing all variables from default or zero values.

- **load_initial**: **Flag to enable loading of initial conditions.** If `True`, the model loads state variables (e.g., soil moisture, groundwater storage) from a specified file to start the simulation.
- **initLoad**: **Path to the file containing initial conditions.** This file should contain the state of relevant variables from the end of a previous run.
- **save_initial**: **Flag to enable saving of initial conditions.** If `True`, the model will save the state of variables at specified time steps for use in future runs.
- **initSave**: **Name prefix for saved initial condition files.**
- **StepInit**: **Date(s) at which initial conditions should be saved.** Format: DD/MM/YYYY. Multiple dates can be specified.

[NETCDF_ATTRIBUTES]

This section defines metadata for NetCDF output files generated by C-CWatM. These attributes help document the origin, purpose, and structure of the data, which is especially important for data sharing, archiving, and reproducibility.

- **institution**: **Name of the institution responsible for the model run.**
- **title**: **Title or description of the NetCDF output.** This provides a brief label for the dataset.
- **metaNetcdfFile**: **Path to the XML metadata file.** This file contains additional metadata definitions for the NetCDF output.

4.2 Process-related settings

These sections configure specific hydrological and water management processes.

[CALIBRATION]

Lists parameters used for model calibration.

[IRRIGATION & LANDCOVER]

Includes land cover types and irrigation-specific parameters.

[SOIL]

Soil properties and constants.

[GROUNDWATER]

Groundwater flow and storage parameters.

[WATERDEMAND]

Water demand data and abstraction settings.

[ROUTING]

River routing configuration.

[LAKES_RESERVOIRS]

Parameters for lake and reservoir behavior.

[INFLOW]

Optimal external inflow configuration (e.g., upstream discharge).

[ENVIRONMENTALFLOW]

Optional environmental flow calculations and thresholds.

4.3 Other technical settings

These sections support data handling and output generation.

[NO_METEO]

Specifies non-meteorological input maps (e.g., runoff, soil moisture).

[METEO]

Conversion factors for meteorological data.

[TOPOP]

Topographic maps for routing and snow modeling.

[MASK_OUTLET]

Defines the spatial mask and outlet locations for the model domain.

[COUPLING]

Settings for coupling with external climate or hydrological models.

[OUTPUT]

Specifies which outputs to generate (maps, time series, averages).

Forcing data and input maps

5.1 Forcing data

Figure 5.1: Overview of C-CWatM forcing variables

C-CWatM requires forcing data for runoff, groundwater recharge (or drainage), root zone soil moisture and evaporation over water. Forcing data should be provided in netCDF format with daily values. C-CWatM expects a separate file for each forcing variable containing data for the whole time period of the model run.

5.1.1 Runoff

Configuration parameters

```
[FILE_PATHS]
PathMeteo = /path/forcing/

[NO_METEO]
# runoff [m]
RunoffMaps = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMeteo)/runoff*

[METEO]
# convert units of forcing data to C-CWatM units [m]
# runoff [m]:
runoff_conversion = 1
```

Data for runoff are read from `RunoffMaps`. The expected unit is `m/day`. Units can be converted using the runoff conversion factor, e.g. `runoff_conversion=0.001` to convert from `mm` to `m`, or `runoff_conversion=24` to convert daily mean values in `m/hour` to daily sums.

5.1.2 Soil water content

The soil water content forcing variable required by C-CWatM is defined as the relative saturation of the root zone. It is expressed as a fraction of the water holding capacity at saturation, where a value of 1 indicates that the root zone is at its maximum water holding capacity. This approach differs from many climate models, where soil water content is represented as relative soil moisture by dividing the water amount in a layer by its thickness. Within C-CWatM, the available water is then derived by multiplying this relative saturation by the soil water storage capacity (`soilWSaterStorageCap`), which is provided by the input file specified under `[SOIL]` in the variable `wsp`.

Configuration parameters

```
[FILE_PATHS]
PathMeteo = /path/forcing/

[NO_METEO]
# Soil Wetness (rootzone)
SMMaps = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMeteo)/rootzoneSM_forcing.nc

[METEO]
# convert units of forcing data to C-CWatM units [m]
# soil water content [%]
soilwater_conversion = 1.
```

Data for root zone soil water content are read from `SMMaps`. The expected unit is `m/m`. Climate models often provide soil moisture in units different from those required by C-CWatM. Simple conversions, such as `%` to `m/m`, can be handled with the `soilwater_conversion` factor. Below are examples of how to convert from other common formats:

1. **Volumetric soil water content:** If soil water content is given relative to the absolute soil volume (rather than to saturation water content), those values need to be divided

by the saturation water holding capacity. Ideally, this should be the value from the original forcing model. If this is not available, the data specified in `wsp=wsirr.nc` can serve as a fallback.

2. **Absolute water content:** If soil moisture is provided as the amount of water in the root zone, it needs to be divided by the water content (in m) at saturation. If this value is not available, first divide by the layer depth (or volume) to obtain relative soil moisture, then proceed as in case 1.
3. **no saturation value available:** In this case, the required values for conversion could be derived e.g. from the Q1 and Q99 quantiles of the soil moisture distribution.

Note: C-CWatM requires root zone soil water content (for calculating irrigation water demand). If the forcing data are provided for multiple soil layers, please compute the mean value for the root zone before applying conversion.

5.1.3 Groundwater recharge

Groundwater recharge (sometimes referred to as drainage in other models) is the process by which water from the soil layer moves downward into the groundwater. In C-CWatM, this represents a source term for the groundwater reservoir. Many climate models do not simulate groundwater and thus drainage is often just implemented as water leaving the water column at the bottom or the sides.

Alternative estimation of groundwater recharge

If groundwater recharge is not provided as an output variable by the forcing model (e.g., when using pre-existing data from CORDEX or CMIP databases), C-CWatM offers a very basic workaround. Please note that this approach is highly simplified and should be applied with caution. In this alternative approach, groundwater recharge can be estimated as a fixed fraction of the runoff for the respective grid cell.

Configuration parameters

```
[FILE_PATHS]
PathMeteo = /path/forcing/

[NO_METEO]
# Groundwater recharge
# RECOMMENDED - use Groundwater recharge
use_GWrecharge = True
# Groundwater Recharge [m]
GWMaps = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMeteo)/sum_gwRecharge*

# if no Groundwater recharge is available, scale with
# runoff [NOT RECOMMENDED]. if used, scale groundwater recharge
# based on runoff using GWscale_factor
# GWrecharge = runoff * GWscale_factor
GWscale_factor = 1.0

[METEO]
# convert units of forcing data to C-CWatM units [m]
# groundwater recharge [m]:
groundwater_conversion = 0.001
```

Data for groundwater recharge are read from `GWMaps`. The expected unit is `m/day`. Units can be converted using the groundwater conversion factor, e.g. `groundwater_conversion=0.001` to convert from `mm` to `m`, or `groundwater_conversion=24` to convert daily mean values in `m/hour` to daily sums. If no groundwater recharge data are available, `use_GWrecharge` is set to `False`. The model then estimates groundwater recharge by multiplying the runoff data with the fraction given in `GWscale_factor`.

5.1.4 Evaporation over water

Evaporation over water surfaces is required to calculate the water balance for rivers, lakes and reservoirs in C-CWatM. Positive fluxes are defined as upwards, i.e. from the water to the atmosphere.

Alternative estimations of open water evaporation

If evaporation over water is not provided as an output variable by the forcing model (e.g., when using pre-existing data from CORDEX or CMIP databases), C-CWatM offers two alternative approaches to estimate this variable. In such cases, evaporation over water can be substituted with potential evaporation (PET), for which various formulas are available in the literature. C-CWatM implements one method based on daily mean temperature and one based on daily mean net radiation. Both methods require these additional forcing variables to be supplied.

1) Calculation based on daily mean temperature

C-CWatM implements a temperature-based empirical equation to calculate PET using the approach described in [Ansoorge and Beran \[2019\]](#). It expresses PET (in `mm/day`) in the form proposed by [Hamon \[1961\]](#):

$$PET = CD^2 P_t, \quad (5.1)$$

where $C = 13.97$ and D are the hours of daylight in units of 12 h. The saturated water density P_t is calculated according to [Xu and Singh \[2001\]](#) as:

$$P_t = 0.0495 \cdot \exp(0.062 T_{mean}), \quad (5.2)$$

where the daily mean temperature T_{mean} is in $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The equations are valid for air temperatures above freezing. For simplicity, we assume that there are always 12 hours of daylight and neglect the term D .

2) Calculation based on daily mean net radiation

In a second empirical approach, PET is estimated based on the net radiation at the surface R_{net} after [Milly and Dunne \[2016\]](#).

$$PET = 0.8(R_{net} - G) \quad (5.3)$$

For simplicity, the contribution of the ground heat flux G is neglected. To convert this value from W/m^2 to `m/day`, we divide by the latent heat of vaporization (2500.9 kJ/kg at 0°C) and multiply by the number of seconds per day.

Configuration parameters

```

[FILE_PATHS]
PathMeteo = /path/forcing/

[NO_METEO]
# Open Water Evaporation
# Different methods to estimate open water evaporation
# OWE - reads in open water evaporation
# T - reads in daily mean temperature, uses Hamon
# Rnet - reads in net radiation, uses energy equivalent of net
  radiation,
# see also Milly and Dunne, 2016
OWE_meth = OWE

# if OWE_meth = OWE
# daily reference evaporation (free water) [m]
OWEMaps = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMeteo)/EWRef*
# if OWE_meth = T
# daily mean temperature [degC]
TMaps = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMeteo)/Temp*
# if OWE_meth = Rnet
# daily mean net radiation [??]
RnMaps = $(FILE_PATHS:PathMeteo)/RNET*

[METEO]
# convert units of forcing data to C-CWatM units [m]
# evaporation over water [m]
evaporation_conversion = 0.001
# only if OWE_meth is not OWE
# conversion factor needed to convert Rnet to Wm2
Rnet_conversion = 1.00
# offset to convert Temperature to C, -273.15 when in K
Temp_offset = 0.0

```

The method for providing data for evaporation over water is controlled by the parameter `OWE_meth`. When `OWE_meth = OWE`, data for evaporation over water are read from `OWEMaps`. The expected unit is m/day. Units can be converted using the evaporation conversion factor, for example `evaporation_conversion=0.001` to convert from mm to m, or `evaporation_conversion=24` to convert daily mean values in m/hour to daily sums.

If no evaporation data are available, evaporation over water can be calculated using daily mean temperature data from `TMaps` by setting `OWE_meth = T`. The expected units is °C, and units can be converted using the temperature conversion offset `Temp_offset`. A third option is `OWE_meth = Rnet`, where evaporation over water is calculated from daily mean net radiation data read from `RnMaps`. The expected units are W/m², and units can be converted using the net radiation conversion factor `Rnet_conversion`.

Re-gridding of evaporation data

In many land surface and hydrological models, evaporation over open water is calculated only for grid cells that explicitly contain a water fraction (e.g. lakes, reservoirs, or rivers). Depending on the source model and dataset, grid cells without water may either be masked or filled with a value of zero. In C-CWatM, missing or masked values in open-water evaporation input fields are internally replaced with 0. While this ensures numerical consistency, it requires special care when spatially re-gridding evaporation fields. In particular, interpolation methods such as bilinear re-gridding will include zero values in the interpolation, which can

lead to unrealistically low evaporation rates in grid cells that contain water. To avoid this issue, a masking strategy can be applied when regridding open-water evaporation fields. One recommended approach is to:

1. Create a binary mask identifying grid cells with valid open-water evaporation values (or water presence).
2. Regrid both the evaporation field and the mask using the same interpolation method (e.g. bilinear).
3. Divide the regridded evaporation field by the regridded mask.

This procedure removes the influence of zero-valued grid cells during interpolation and preserves physically consistent evaporation rates over water bodies.

```
# regridding of evaporation
cdo remapbil,target_grid.nc evaporation_original.nc evap_regridded.nc
# create a mask from evaporation data (summer, no ice)
cdo expr,mask=(abs(EVAPW)>0.00000001)?1:0 evaporation_original.nc
    mask_summer.nc
# remap mask
cdo remapbil,target_grid.nc mask_summer.nc mask_regridded.nc
# divide evaporation by regridded water mask
cdo div evap_regridded.nc mask_regridded.nc evap.nc
# optional, to fill neighboring cells
cdo remapnn,target_grid.nc evap.nc evap_filled.nc
```

5.2 Input maps

5.2.1 Downloads

Input maps for CWatM exist for 30 arcmin and 5 arcmin. The 30 arcmin data can be downloaded from:

<https://github.com/iiasa/CWatM-Earth-30min>

and the 5 arcmin data from google drive:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1HqcBj5fD6DHJp0e-t_6JHFMKFtubghZf

or the IIASA-ftp server:

ftp://rcwatm:Water1090@ftp.iiasa.ac.at/cwatm_input_5min.zip.

Note that for C-CWatM, not all of the datasets provided in those repositories are required. Additional datasets for C-CWatM include the soil parameters `wsirr.nc`, `wfcirr.nc`, `wwpirr.nc`, that are available in the folder `input_soil` on <https://github.com/UWaRes/c-cwatm/>.

5.2.2 Required input maps

1. Topography and Grid Definition
 - `routing/ldd.nc` - local drain direction
 - `landsurface/topo/elvstd.nc` - elevation standard deviation
 - `landsurface/topo/cellarea.nc` - grid cell area
2. Soil, land cover and crops

- soil_ccwatm/wsirr.nc - soil water storage capacity
 - soil_ccwatm/wfcirr.nc - field capacity
 - soil_ccwatm/wwpirr.nc - wilting point
 - landsurface/fractionLandcover.nc - land-cover fractions (dynamic)
 - landcover/irrPaddy/cropCoefficientirrPaddy_10days.nc - paddy crops
 - landcover/irrNonPaddy/cropCoefficientirrNonPaddy_10days.nc - non-paddy crops
3. Sectoral water demand
- landsurface/waterDemand/irrigationArea.nc - historical irrigation area
 - landsurface/waterDemandhistorical_dom_year_millionm3_5min_1961_2010.nc - domestic demand
 - landsurface/waterDemandhistorical_ind_year_millionm3_5min_1961_2010.nc - industrial demand
 - landsurface/waterDemandhistorical_liv_year_millionm3_5min_1961_2010.nc - livestock demand
4. Routing Parameters
- routing/kinematic/changradient.nc - channel slope
 - routing/kinematic/chanmanning.nc - Manning's roughness
 - routing/kinematic/chanlength.nc - channel length
 - routing/kinematic/chanwidth.nc - channel width
 - routing/kinematic/chanheight.nc - channel depth
5. Lakes, reservoirs and ground water
- routing/lakesreservoirs/lakesResID.nc - water-body IDs
 - routing/lakesreservoirs/lakesResType.nc - type (lake / reservoir)
 - routing/lakesreservoirs/lakesResDis.nc - average discharge
 - routing/lakesreservoirs/lakesResArea.nc - surface area
 - routing/lakesreservoirs/lakesResVolRes.nc - reservoir volume
 - routing/lakesreservoirs/lakesResYear.nc - construction year
 - routing/lakesreservoirs/smallLakesRes.nc - small water bodies
 - routing/lakesreservoirs/smallLakesResDis.nc - average discharge
 - groundwater/recessionCoeff.nc - groundwater recession coefficient
6. Forcing Maps (if not provided by coupling) These datasets could be obtained, e.g., from a (regional) climate model or a reanalysis.
- runoff*.nc - runoff
 - rootzoneSM*.nc - root-zone soil moisture (forcing)
 - sum_gwRecharge*.nc - groundwater recharge
 - EWRef*.nc - open-water evaporation

An overview of the data sources can be found in Tab. 5.1.

Table 5.1: C-CWatM input maps. Adapted from Burek et al. [2020], their Tab. 1.

Dataset	Source	Original spatial resolution	Submodule in CWatM
Elevation	SRTM [Jarvis et al., 2008]; Hydro1k [USGS, 2002]	3', 1 km	Water demand
Flow direction map	DDM30 [Döll and Lehner, 2002]; DRT [Wu et al., 2011]	30' and 5'	Routing, lakes
Lakes and reservoirs	HydroLakes database [Messenger et al., 2016, Lehner et al., 2011]	Shapefile	Lakes, routing
Groundwater	GLHYMPS [Huscroft et al., 2018]	–	Groundwater
Land cover	Landcover fraction derived for CWatM [Burek et al., 2020]	5'	Land cover
	Irrigated areas [Döll and Siebert, 2002, Siebert et al., 2005, 2010]	5'	Water demand
Crop coefficient	MIRCA2000 (Portmann et al., 2010)	5'	Irrigation
Population and GDP	Hyde 3.2 database [Klein Goldewijk et al., 2017]	5'	Water demand
	SSP Database at IIASA [Riahi et al., 2017] SSP population and GDP projections: Spatial disaggregation on 30" and 5' [Jones and O'Neill, 2016, Gao, 2017, Kummu et al., 2018, Gidden et al., 2018]	Country 7.5', 0.5'	

The need for calibration depends on the intended application of the model. For use cases requiring close agreement with observations, such as water resources management or impact assessments, calibration can improve model performance. However, calibration may increase dependence on observational data availability, potentially leading to overfitting in data-rich regions and higher uncertainty in data-scarce areas. It can also obscure structural model uncertainties and compensate for biases in input data. Calibration in C-CWatM is therefore optional. Users should carefully assess whether calibration is appropriate for their objectives. Calibration can be performed at global, regional, or catchment scales.

Examples of calibration routines are provided at

https://github.com/UWaRes/c-cwatm_calibration

6.1 Model calibration

As in CWatM, calibration in C-CWatM is implemented using the DEAP evolutionary computation framework [Fortin et al., 2012], employing the NSGA-II algorithm [Deb et al., 2002] in a single-objective optimization setup. Model performance is evaluated using the modified Kling–Gupta efficiency (KGE) [Kling et al., 2012], which assesses the agreement between simulated and observed river discharge by jointly considering correlation, bias, and flow variability. KGE balances these three components in a single metric, providing a robust objective function that avoids some of the limitations of commonly used alternatives such as the Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency, which can overly emphasize high flows or be sensitive to bias. The optimal value of KGE is 1, corresponding to perfect agreement between simulations and observations. More details can be found in the CWatM documentation.

https://cwatm.iiasa.ac.at/56_calibration.html

A list of recommended calibration parameters is provided in in Tab. 6.1. Compared to CWatM, C-CWatM includes fewer land surface processes, and therefore we keep only 6 of the 12 calibration parameters originally suggested for CWatM. We extended the list by the 'alpha depletion' variable, which defines the upper soil moisture threshold up to which farmers irrigate. This variable is likely of importance for studies focused on irrigation and could also be set to a fixed value based on a priori knowledge.

Table 6.1: Optional C-CWatM calibration parameters.

Module	Variable description	Variable name	
		Default	value
Soil	Infiltration capacity parameter: empirical shape parameter b of the ARNO model	arnoBeta_add:	0.39 [0.01, 1.2]
Routing	Channel Manning’s n factor: roughness factor in channel routing	manningsN:	1.86 [0.1, 10]
Groundwater	Recession coefficient factor: factor to adjust the base flow recession constant (the contribution from groundwater to baseflow)	recessionCoeff_factor:	5.278 [0.1, 10.0]
Reservoirs and lakes	Normal storage limit: the fraction of storage capacity used as normal storage limit	normalStorageLimit:	0.44 [0.15, 0.85]
	Lake “A” factor: factor to channel width and weir coefficient as a part of the Poleni’s weir equation	lakeAFactor:	0.33 [0.33, 3.0]
	Lake and river evaporation factor: adjust open water evaporation	lakeEvaFactor:	1.52 [0.5, 3.0]
Water demand	Alpha depletion for irrigation: farmers irrigate only up to a fraction of field capacity	alphaDepl:	0.7 [0.5, 1.0]

6.2 Regionalisation of calibration parameters

In the following, we propose a method for regionalising calibration parameter maps (see also https://github.com/UWaRes/c-cwatm_calibration). Catchment-based regionalisation of calibration parameters, allowing calibrated parameter sets to be transferred from gauged to ungauged regions. This approach enables the derivation of spatially consistent parameter fields while maintaining physically meaningful parameter values in areas without discharge observations.

The regionalisation strategy follows the physio-climatic similarity approach proposed by Beck et al. [2016]. In a first step, calibration parameters are individually optimized for each gauged calibration station, based on the upstream contributing basin. In a second step, these calibrated parameter sets are transferred to ungauged catchments using a similarity-based regionalisation scheme. For each ungauged catchment, similarity is evaluated with respect to all gauged upstream catchments, based on selected physio-climatic characteristics known to be strong predictors of hydrological behavior [Beck et al., 2015].

Dissimilarity between a gauged and an ungauged catchment is quantified using a normalized distance metric:

$$S = \sum_p \frac{|Z_{ungauged}^p - Z_{gauged}^p|}{IQR(p)} \quad (6.1)$$

where Z^p denotes one of the physio-climatic predictors p , and $IQR(p)$ is the interquartile range of predictor p across all catchments. Normalization by the interquartile range ensures that predictors with different units and magnitudes contribute comparably to the overall dissimilarity score.

The github repository contains examples using 3 predictors that are based on those identified by [Beck et al., 2015] as being strongly linked to catchment hydrological signatures:

- Mean annual precipitation
- Aridity index, defined as the ratio of precipitation to potential evapotranspiration
- Mean surface slope

For each ungauged catchment, the three most similar gauged catchments (i.e. those with the lowest dissimilarity S) are selected as donor basins. The final parameter set assigned to the ungauged catchment is computed as the mean of the calibrated parameter sets from these three donors. Using multiple donor catchments reduces sensitivity to individual basins with atypical hydrological behavior or data quality issues and has been shown to improve robustness and overall model performance in regionalisation studies. This regionalisation approach allows C-CWatM to generate spatially distributed parameter fields that are consistent across gauged and ungauged regions, while explicitly linking parameter values to identifiable physio-climatic controls.

C-CWatM supports fully coupled simulations with (regional) climate models through the OASIS3-MCT coupling framework. OASIS3-MCT provides a robust and widely used infrastructure for synchronized data exchange, parallel communication, and grid remapping between model components, facilitating interoperability with a broad range of climate models. Its non-intrusive coupling approach minimizes code modifications within C-CWatM, with coupling behavior configured externally via the `namcouple` file.

Integration with C-CWatM is achieved through the pyOASIS Python interface, which enables efficient data exchange while maintaining compatibility with parallelized climate model workflows. The coupling interface in C-CWatM is activated conditionally via the settings file and is implemented in a dedicated module, ensuring a clear separation between core model functionality and coupling logic.

7.1 Installing OASIS3-MCT (on Levante at DKRZ)

General OASIS3-MCT documentation can be found in:

- [user guide \(pdf\)](#)
- `tutorial_communication.pdf` in `.../oasis3_mct/examples/tutorial_communication/`

7.1.1 Obtain OASIS3-MCT

To obtain the OASIS3-MCT code, registration at CERFACS ([here](#)) is required. The library can then be downloaded from gitlab:

```
git clone https://gitlab.com/cerfacs/oasis3-mct.git
```

7.1.2 Compile OASIS3-MCT

For compilation, see OASIS User Guide section [6.1](#):

- The compilation uses `oasis3-MCT/util/make_dir/TopMakefileOasis3`, this includes `make.inc`, which points to the platform specific file `make.levante`.
- The root of the OASIS3-MCT tree can be anywhere, but it must be defined by the variable `COUPLE`; `ARCHDIR` defines the location of the compilation directory.
- The OASIS3-MCT library should be compiled with the same compilers and system software as any coupled model component using it (defined in `comp_env_levante.sh`).

- Error messages are written in `COMP.err` and `COMP.log`.

The following adjustments have to be made for compilation on levante:

1. load modules and set paths and variables in `comp_env_levante.sh`
2. specify libraries and compilers in `make.levante`

Compilation environment

Example of `comp_env_levante.sh`:

```
#!/bin/ksh
# Compilation environment
source /etc/profile.d/modules.sh
module purge
# gcc compiler
module load intel-oneapi-compilers/2022.0.1-gcc-11.2.0
# mpi
module load openmpi/4.1.2-intel-2021.5.0
# netcdf libraries
module load netcdf-fortran/4.5.3-openmpi-4.1.2-intel-2021.5.0
module load netcdf-c/4.8.1-openmpi-4.1.2-intel-2021.5.0

echo 'We work on levante'
echo 'which mpirun'
export MPIRUN=mpirun
export corespn=128

# --- for REMO ---
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/sw/spack-levante/
      netcdf-fortran-4.5.3-k6xq5g/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
export OMPI_MCA_pml="ucx"
export OMPI_MCA_btl=self
export OMPI_MCA_osc="pt2pt"
export UCX_IB_ADDR_TYPE=ib_global
# for most runs one may or may not want to disable HCOLL
export OMPI_MCA_coll="^ml,hcoll"
export OMPI_MCA_coll_hcoll_enable="0"
export HCOLL_ENABLE_MCAST_ALL="0"
export HCOLL_MAIN_IB=mlx5_0:1
export UCX_NET_DEVICES=mlx5_0:1
```

Makefile

Example of `make.levante`:

```
# Include file for OASIS3 Makefile
# CHAN : communication technique used in OASIS3 (MPI1/MPI2)
CHAN          = MPI1
# --- Paths for libraries, object files and binaries ---
# COUPLE : path for oasis3-mct main directory
COUPLE        = $(OASIS_COUPLE)
# ARCHDIR : directory created when compiling
ARCHDIR       = $(COUPLE)/INSTALL_OASIS.$(OASIS_ENV)
# MPI command (for pyoasis scripts)
MPIRUN        = mpirun --oversubscribe
# NETCDF library
NETCDFFF_DIR  = /sw/spack-levante/netcdf-fortran-4.5.3-k6xq5g
```

```

NETCDFC_DIR      = /sw/spack-levante/netcdf-c-4.8.1-2k3cmu
NETCDFF_INC     = -I$(NETCDFF_DIR)/include
NETCDFC_INC     = -I$(NETCDFC_DIR)/include
NETCDFF_LIB     = $(NETCDFF_DIR)/lib
NETCDFC_LIB     = $(NETCDFC_DIR)/lib
NETCDFF_MOD     = -I$(NETCDFF_LIB)
NETCDF_LIBRARY = -Wl,-rpath,$(NETCDFF_LIB) -L$(NETCDFF_LIB)
                -Wl,-rpath,$(NETCDFC_LIB) -L$(NETCDFC_LIB) -lnetcdff -lnetcdf
# Make command
MAKE            = gmake
# Compilers
F90             = mpifort
F               = $(F90)
f90            = $(F90)
f              = $(F90)
CC             = mpicc
# Static archiver
AR             = ar # xiar??
ARFLAGS        = -ruv
# Linker (needed for shared libraries)
LD             = $(F90)
# Shared libraries options
DYNOPT         = -fPIC
LDDYNOPT      = -shared
# Fortran libraries for C linking
F2C_LIBS      = -lifcore -lifcoremt -lifport -limf
# CPP keys and compiler options
CPPDEF        = -Duse_comm_$(CHAN) -D__VERBOSE -DTREAT_OVERLAY -DYAC_REMAP
CCBASEFLAGS   :=
# INC_DIR : includes all *mod for each library
INC_DIR       = -I$(ARCHDIR)/include
# FLIBS : for toys when linking in local Makefile
FLIBS         = $(NETCDF_LIBRARY)
#
F90FLAGS      = $(FCBASEFLAGS) $(INC_DIR) $(CPPDEF) $(NETCDFF_INC)
              $(NETCDFF_MOD)
f90FLAGS      = $(FCBASEFLAGS) $(INC_DIR) $(CPPDEF) $(NETCDFF_INC)
              $(NETCDFF_MOD)
FFLAGS        = $(FCBASEFLAGS) $(INC_DIR) $(CPPDEF) $(NETCDFF_INC)
              $(NETCDFF_MOD)
fFLAGS        = $(FCBASEFLAGS) $(INC_DIR) $(CPPDEF) $(NETCDFF_INC)
              $(NETCDFF_MOD)
CCFLAGS       = $(CCBASEFLAGS) $(INC_DIR) $(CPPDEF) $(NETCDFC_INC)
              $(NETCDFF_MOD)
LDLFLAGS      = $(FCBASEFLAGS)
F2C_LDFLAGS   = $(F2C_LIBS)

```

Compilation

```

export OASIS_ENV=levante
export OASIS_COUPLE=/home/g/g300116/test_oasis/oasis3-mct

cd /home/g/g300116/test_oasis/oasis3-mct/util/make_dir
. ./comp_env_levante.sh
make -f TopMakefileOasis3

```

For new compilation: `make -f TopMakefileOasis3 realclean` (removes all OASIS3-MCT compiled sources and libraries)

7.1.3 Run example

OASIS3-MCT (for fortran) can be tested either now or later after pyOASIS has been installed (7.2.3). For testing, use the toy model in `.../oasis3-mct/examples/tutorial_communication/`.

- With the same prerequisites as for OASIS3-MCT, compile with `make`.
- Adjust the runfile `run_tutorial` for levante. See example for pyOASIS toy model (7.2.3) for specifics.
- Run toy model with `./run_tutorial`.

7.2 Installing pyOASIS (on Levante)

pyOASIS documentation can be found at:

- [technical report \(pdf\)](#)
- [user guide \(online\)](#)

7.2.1 Compile pyOASIS

Compilation as for OASIS, but with added pyoasis:

```
export OASIS_ENV=levante
export OASIS_COUPLE=/home/g/g300116/test_oasis/oasis3-mct

cd /home/g/g300116/test_oasis/oasis3-mct/util/make_dir
. ./comp_env_levante.sh
make -f TopMakefileOasis3 pyoasis

# before running the model
source /home/g/g300116/test_oasis/oasis3-mct/INSTALL_OASIS.levante/
python/init.sh
```

7.2.2 Python environment

Create environment

Create a conda environment `mpi_env` on levante:

```
source .bashrc # for conda
module load openmpi/4.1.2-intel-2021.5.0 # for correct mpi version

conda create -n mpi_env -c conda-forge python=3.10
conda activate mpi_env
# -- required for pyoasis --
pip install numpy
pip install netcdf4

MPICC=$(which mpicc) pip install --no-binary=mpi4py mpi4py
--force-reinstall --no-cache-dir
```

NOTE: It is important that `mpi4py` is installed with the correct MPI module loaded. Otherwise the versions are not compatible and there will be an error! `--force-reinstall` ensures that conda does not default to the `mpi4py` version that is already installed on levante.

Activate environment in slurm job

To activate the conda environment correctly during a slurm job, add the following lines to the batch script:

```
ulimit -s unlimited
module purge
# Load OpenMPI first (same one used when building mpi4py)
module load openmpi/4.1.2-intel-2021.5.0
# Activate your conda environment
source ~/.bashrc # or source /path/to/conda/etc/profile.d/conda.sh
conda activate mpi_env
# set pyoasis variables
source /home/g/g300116/test_oasis/oasis3-mct/INSTALL_OASIS.levante/
python/init.sh
```

7.2.3 Toy model

The toy model can be used to test whether the installation worked and OASIS runs as expected. The toy model contains small dummy models for atmosphere and ocean - each written either in fortran or python.

Obtain toy model

- clone toy model directory with
`git clone https://earth.bsc.es/gitlab/rmarti1/oasis-toy-model-python.git`
- change paths in fortran/Makefile and python/Makefile to include `make.levante` in OASIS directory:
`/home/g/g300116/test_oasis/oasis3-mct/util/make_dir/make.inc`
- same preparation as for OASIS/pyOASIS compilation:

```
export OASIS_ENV=levante
export OASIS_COUPLE=/home/g/g300116/test_oasis/oasis3-mct
cd /home/g/g300116/test_oasis/oasis3-mct/util/make_dir
. ./comp_env_levante.sh
```

- run `make` in toy model root folder

Run toy model

In `oasis-toy-model-python/run_example.sh` change respective paths, creation of jobfile and run command.

```
## - Define architecture
arch=levante
casename=test1
...
if [ ${arch} == levante ] ; then
  echo 'writing for levante'
  cat <<EOF > $rundir/run_${casename}.${sarch}
#!/bin/bash
#
#SBATCH --job-name=spoc          # Specify job name
#SBATCH --partition=compute     # Specify partition name for job
  execution
```

```

#SBATCH --nodes=2
#SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=$nproc_exe1
#SBATCH --exclusive
#SBATCH --time=00:03:00          # Set a limit on the total run time
#SBATCH --account=ch0636        # Charge resources on this project
                                account
#SBATCH --output=$rundir/$casename.o
#SBATCH --error=$rundir/$casename.e

ulimit -s unlimited
module purge
# Load OpenMPI first (same one used when building mpi4py)
module load openmpi/4.1.2-intel-2021.5.0
# Activate your conda environment
source ~/.bashrc # or source /path/to/conda/etc/profile.d/conda.sh
conda activate mpi_env
# pyoasis variables
source /home/g/g300116/test_oasis/oasis3-mct/INSTALL_OASIS.levante/
python/init.sh

cd $rundir

time mpirun --mca opal_common_ucx_opal_mem_hooks 1 -np $nproc_exe1
    $exe1 : -np $nproc_exe2 $exe2
EOF
fi

```

Execute model with:

```

if [ ${arch} == levante ]; then
    echo 'Submitting the job to queue using sbatch'
    sbatch $rundir/run_${casename}.${arch}
    squeue -u $user
fi

```

7.3 Implementation of the coupling interface in C-CWatM

Building on C-CWatM's general model structure, all functionalities related to the OASIS3-MCT coupler are grouped in the file `management_modules/pyoasis_cpl.py`, which contains the `pyoasis_cpl()` class, as well as additional coupling functions. Like all other processes in C-CWatM, `pyoasis_cpl()` consists of the methods `initial()`, which is called in `cwatm_inital.py`, and `dynamic()`, which is called in `cwatm_dynamic.py`. The coupling routine is only called when the newly introduced flag `coupl_flag` in the settings file is set to `'oasis_cpl'`. This structure allows for an implementation with only minimal changes in the main C-CWatM code.

The function `initial()` groups all code required for the initialization of OASIS3-MCT, while `dynamic()` performs the data exchange at specified time steps. During model initialization, the `initial()` method sets up the coupling interface by creating an OASIS component for C-CWatM using `pyoasis.Component()` and defining the local MPI communicator and grid partitioning using `pyoasis.SerialPartition()`. The C-CWatM grid and the corresponding land-sea-mask are written to netCDF files using `pyoasis.Grid()`. The coupling fields, which are the required forcing variables runoff, groundwater recharge, soil moisture, and evaporation over water, are defined using `pyoasis.Var()`. The names of the coupling variables defined here have to match the declarations in the `namcouple` file.

The `dynamic()` method manages the exchange of data between the different OASIS model components. At each exchange interval – defined in the `namcouple` configuration file – C-

CWatM receives the variables specified in the initial phase using the pyOASIS `get()` method. If the units of the received variables differ from those expected by C-CWatM, conversion factors are applied. These factors can be defined in the settings file under [METEO] using the format `conv_<varname>`. After applying the C-CWatM land mask, the received fields are assigned to the corresponding internal C-CWatM variables: runoff (`runoff`), groundwater recharge (`sum_gwRecharge`), soil moisture (`rootzoneSM`), and evaporation over water (`EWRef`). If C-CWatM should be configured to send fields to the second model coupled to C-CWatM (e.g. the amount of irrigation water), this would also be implemented in the `dynamic()` method using the pyOASIS `put()` function. Note that any additional variables intended for exchange must be declared and initialized in the `initial()` method and in the `namcouple` file.

7.3.1 Implementation in the model code

New routines

`pyoasis_cpl.py`:

This class contains all the functionality related to initializing and managing data exchange through the pyOASIS coupler. It handles grid setup, partitioning, and the declaration and transfer of coupling fields between C-CWatM and external models.

```
def initial(self):
    # Initialize the OASIS coupling interface for the C-CWatM
    hydrological component.
    # 1) initialize component
    oasis_component = pyoasis.Component("hydro_component")
    # 2) get local communicator and define partition using
    self.oasis_specify_partition -> uses pyoasis.SerialPartition
    # 3) grid definition using
    create_2d_ccwatm_grid from grid_tools
    # write oasis grid information using
    self.oasis_define_grid -> uses grid=pyoasis.Grid, grid.set_mask()
    # 4) declaration of coupling fields
    # needs to match namcouple
    self.var.oasisvar_id = [None] * 4
    self.var.oasisvar_id[0] = pyoasis.Var("ccwatm_recv_runoff", ...)
    self.var.oasisvar_id[1] = pyoasis.Var("ccwatm_recv_gwRecharge",
    ...)
    # same for EWRef and rootzoneSM
    # 5) termination of definition phase
    oasis_component.enddef()
```

```
def dynamic(self):
    # Receive and send data via OASIS.
    # 1) OASIS get for each variable as:
    field_recv_runoff = pyoasis.asarray(...)
    self.var.oasisvar_id[0].get(seconds_passed, field_recv_runoff)
    ...
    # 2) assign to C-CWatM variables and apply landmask and
    conversion factors
    mapnp1 = np.ma.masked_array(np.flipud(field_recv_runoff.T),
    maskinfo['mask'])
    mapnp1 = np.ma.compressed(mapnp1)
    self.var.runoff = np.maximum(0., mapnp1 * self.var.conv_runoff)
    ...
```

`grid_tools.py`:

Functions related to the model grid that are required for the OASIS grids.nc file.

```
create_2d_ccwatm_grid # Generate 2D arrays of longitude and latitude
                      coordinates for a C-CWatM regular grid.
compute_grid_corners # Compute the corner coordinates of grid cells
                      from center coordinates.
compute_grid_cell_areas # Compute the area of each grid cell on a
                        spherical Earth using corner coordinates.
unrot_coordinates # Convert rotated latitude and longitude
                  coordinates to unrotated (geographic) coordinates.
```

jobscript_ccwatm.sh:

Load all required modules and the python environment; start coupled model run with `mpirun`.

```
#!/bin/bash
#SBATCH -- ... # batch job specifications
# Load required modules
module load openmpi/4.1.2-intel-2021.5.0
# Activate conda environment (containing pyOASIS)
conda activate mpi_env
# pyoasis variables
source /home/g/g300116/test_oasis/oasis3-mct/INSTALL_OASIS.levante/
python/init.sh
# model run
mpirun -np 1 python3 run_cwatm.py settings.ini : run_coupled_model2
```

namcouple:

Define the number of field to be exchanged and the length of the model run. For each coupling variable, define:

- field names and exchange frequency
- grid names (as stored in `grids.nc` and `masks.nc`)
- methods concerning regridding or data analysis (e.g. with SCRIPR)

Changes in existing routines

`cwatm_initial.py`:

If the coupling flag is set to `oasis_cpl`, an instance of the `pyoasis_cpl` class is initiated during the initialization phase of C-CWatM and the `initial` function of the class is called (before `readmeteo`).

```
if binding['coupl_flag']=='oasis_cpl':
    from cwatm.management_modules.pyoasis_cpl import pyoasis_cpl
    self.pyoasis_cpl_module = pyoasis_cpl(self)
...
if binding['coupl_flag']=='oasis_cpl':
    self.pyoasis_cpl_module.initial()
```

`cwatm_dynamic.py`:

If the coupling flag is set to `oasis_cpl`, the `dynamic` function of the `pyoasis_cpl` class is called during the time loop of C-CWatM. It replaces parts of `readmeteo`.

```
if binding['coupl_flag']=='oasis_cpl':
    self.pyoasis_cpl_module.dynamic()
```

`miscInitial.py`:

Introduce conversion factors for the forcing data, e.g. to convert *mm* to *m*. Read from `settingsfile`.

```
# Read conversion factors for forcing data
self.var.conv_runoff = loadmap('runoff_conversion')
self.var.conv_groundw = loadmap('groundwater_conversion')
self.var.conv_evap = loadmap('evaporation_conversion')
self.var.conv_soilw = loadmap('soilwater_conversion')
```

readmeteo.py:

1) Check if OASIS has been initialized properly when forcing variables are provided via OASIS.

```
elif binding['coupl_flag']=='oasis_coupl':
    # check if oasis has been initialized
    # oasisvar_id should contain at least the 4 forcing variables
    if len(self.var.oasisvar_id) < 4:
        # TODO: raise error
        print('Not all 4 required forcing variables are exchanged via
OASIS.')
    else:
        print('Forcing data will be received using OASIS.')
```

2) If no_coupl is set, multiply the loaded forcing variables by the conversion factors.

```
self.var.runoff = np.maximum(0., self.var.runoff *
self.var.conv_runoff)
self.var.sum_gwRecharge = np.maximum(0., self.var.sum_gwRecharge *
self.var.conv_groundw)
self.var.rootzoneSM = np.maximum(0., self.var.rootzoneSM *
self.var.conv_soilw)
self.var.EWRef = self.var.EWRef * self.var.conv_evap
```

settings_**.ini:

New options in the settingfile.

1) Set the coupling flag coupl_flag to either no_coupl for reading in forcing files (standard method as in CWatM), or oasis_cpl when forcing data is provided by another (dummy-) model via OASIS.

```
#-----
[COUPLING]
#-----
# flag to define type of coupling:
# no_coupl - input data is already provided on C-CWatM grid
# oasis_coupl - use OASIS3-MCT coupler
coupl_flag = oasis_coupl
```

2) Define conversion factors for forcing data. Used in both methods (coupling/no-coupling).

```
[METEO]
# convert units of forcing data to C-CWatM units
# e.g. 0.001 for mm -> m
# runoff [m]:
runoff_conversion = 0.001
# groundwater recharge [m]:
groundwater_conversion = 0.001
# evaporation over water [m]
evaporation_conversion = 0.001
# soil water content [%]
soilwater_conversion = 1.
```

7.3.2 Using OASIS to read forcing data

OASIS can also be used to efficiently handle the regridding when forcing data on a different grid is used. For each new data source (model or other dataset), a new file like `run_oasis_forcing_modelname.py` needs to be created. For each new model, the functions in `coupling.py` (and possibly `grid_tools.py`) have to be adjusted, as well as the grid names in `namcouple`.

New routines

`run_oasis_dummy.py` (should be `run_oasis_forcing_remo.py`):

A python file that acts a second coupled model with the single purpose to read forcing data for each time step and send the fields to C-CWatM.

```
def read_remo_info(binding, starttime):
    # Read grid, landmask, and other auxiliary information for REMO.

    ### ----- Initialization ----- ###
    # --- get info from settings file using ---
    coupling.parse_settings_file
    coupling.read_modelrun_info
    # --- initialize reading of forcing data ---
    meteoforc = coupling.MeteoForc2Var(...)
    # --- read remo grid information and other info ---
    read_remo_info(...)
    # --- initialize OASIS coupler ---
    # transpose REMO grid to match C-CWatM orientation
    coupling.init_oasis_forcing(...)

    ### ----- Time loop ----- ###
    for t in np.arange(simulated_days):
        # --- read REMO forcing for each variable ---
        meteoforc.read_forcing(currenttime, 'runoff',
                               binding['COUPLING']['RunoffName'])
        ...
        # ----- get and put as -----
        var_id[0].put(seconds_passed, meteoforc.runoff.values.T)
        ...

    # --- finalize OASIS ---
    del comp
```

`coupling.py`:

Functions and classes required to read forcing data and exchange them with C-CWatM via OASIS. 1) A class to handle meteorological forcing data from climate models.

```
read_forcing # Read and extract meteorological forcing data for a
              specific date and variable.
varnames_dict # For each model flag, define the mapping of variable
              flags to dataset variable names and filename identifiers.
get_filename # For each model flag, construct the full path to the
              NetCDF file for a given variable and date.
```

2) Functions used to read model run info and initialize OASIS

```
parse_settings_file # Get values from C-CWatM settingsfile.
read_modelrun_info # Extract the model run start time and number of
                  simulated days from the C-
def init_oasis_forcing(nlon_forcing, nlat_forcing, lon_2d, lat_2d,
                      landmask_input):
```

```

# Initializes the OASIS coupling interface for the forcing
component.
# 1) initialize component
comp = pyoasis.Component("forcing_component")
# 2) get local communicator and define partition using
self.oasis_specify_partition -> uses pyoasis.SerialPartition
# 3) grid definition using
create_2d_ccwatm_grid from grid_tools
# write oasis grid information using
self.oasis_define_grid -> uses grid=pyoasis.Grid, grid.set_mask()
# 4) declaration of coupling fields
# needs to match namcouple
self.var.oasisvar_id = [None] * 4
var_id[0] = pyoasis.Var("FIELD_SEND_runoff", ...)
self.var.oasisvar_id[1] = pyoasis.Var("FIELD_SEND_gwRecharge",
...)
# same for EWRef and rootzoneSM
# 5) termination of definition phase
comp.enddef()

```

3) Specific functions used for the 'remo' model

```

parse_dates # Converts the time axis of a REMO xarray dataset from
absolute time values to datetime.
num2date(num) # Convert a numeric absolute date value to datetime
object.

```

jobscript_ccwatm.sh:

Run both models with

```

settingsfile="settings_CCWatM_5min_example.ini"
mpirun -np 1 python3 run_ccwatm.py "$settingsfile" : \
    -np 1 python3 run_oasis_dummy.py "$settingsfile"

```

Changes in existing routines

settings_*.ini:

Define the name of the model that was used to produce the forcing data (used in coupling.py). Provide the path and (if necessary) a filename prefix for the forcing data.

```

#-----
[COUPLING]
#-----
# flag to define type of coupling:
# no_coupl - input data is already provided on C-CWatM grid
# oasis_coupl - use OASIS3-MCT coupler
coupl_flag = oasis_coupl
# ---- if 'no_coupl' is selected the following settings are not used
----
# model used for forcing/coupling
# list of models: remo
fmodel_flag = remo
# path where meteorological forcing data are stored in .nc format
# for remo: stored in yearly folders ../YYYY/
PathForc =
    /work/ch0636/projects/uwares/CWatM_forcing/Remo_ERA5_27lev/
    daily_means/
# (part of) filenames of forcing files
# runoff

```

```
RunoffName = e100001n
# groundwater recharge
GWName = e100001n
# evaporation over water
OWName = e100001n
# soil water content
SMName = e100001n
```

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